

FROM CUSTODIANS OF CULTURE TO MARGINALIZED CITIZENS: THE DILEMMA OF THE AGED IN IKOT EKPENE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Social and cultural changes are essential elements of every society. The values of the aged in Nigerian communities, particularly in the Southern part of the country, are changing rapidly. This qualitative research aimed to examine the challenges faced by the elderly in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study investigates how the elderly are marginalised in decision-making and neglected in the distribution of relief palliatives within Ikot Ekpene. The disengagement theory of ageing and the Activity Theory served as the theoretical framework. A survey research design was used, and Fetterman's big-net approach was employed for sampling and determining the sample size. Participants were recruited from Utu Ikpe, Mbiaso, and Ifuho communities. An interview guide was developed for the purpose of data collection. The data were analysed thematically, aligned with the key themes related to the study's objectives. The findings revealed that youths perceive the elders as non-key actors in politics, marginalising them in important decisions within their communities. Additionally, many relief palliatives intended for the elderly were diverted for personal gain by influential figures. The study concludes that the aged in Ikot Ekpene have not been given their deserved position in the affairs of their communities and welfare programmes. It is recommended that the government establish a dedicated ministry, such as the "Ministry of the Aged Affairs," to enhance the social well-being of the elderly, recognising their vital contributions to community growth and cultural preservation as custodians of tradition and socialisation agents.

Keywords: Aged, dilemma, marginalisation, politics, and Ikot Ekpene

INTRODUCTION

Every stage of life brings its own wisdom and challenges. In some societies, older individuals are highly regarded, whereas in others, they may be perceived as a burden. Similar to gender stratification, age stratification differs across cultures. Societies around the globe employ various forms of age stratification that correspond to specific cultural roles and privileges associated with different life stages. In traditional African societies, older individuals

were greatly valued for their significant contributions in uniting the community, preserving cultural values, passing down knowledge and skills, resolving conflicts, and educating the youth. The traditional African community generally holds favourable views of older individuals, providing them with the finest food and beverages, and their opinions were highly esteemed and respected. Scholars such as anthropologists, sociologists, and political scientists categorise these societies as gerontocracies, which are systems of governance led by older individuals (Abanyam, 2013).

It has been revealed that in traditional societies, older individuals were frequently granted a significant level of respect. In cultures that featured age-grades, elders typically held a primary and often final authority on matters of importance to the community. Within familial structures, the influence of both men and women generally increased with age. In traditional African society, family and friends provide care for older individuals at home until their final days. There existed a prevailing attitude that parents made considerable sacrifices for their children, and in return, their adult children were expected to make sacrifices for their ageing parents (Abanyam 2011). However, shifts in the structure of African society have diminished the privileges that older individuals once enjoyed. These transformations have led to the emergence of numerous challenges that older individuals did not previously encounter. Consequently, this study aims to explore the evolving privileges and challenges faced by older individuals in modern African society.

The swift increase in the ageing demographic, that is, individuals aged 60 and above, has been progressing for an extended period in numerous African nations. For instance, in Ghana, the population of older individuals grew from 213,477 in 1960 to 1,643,381 in 2010, with women constituting 56 percent and men 44 percent of the population aged 60 and older (Ghana Statistical Service, 2013). In Uganda, the elderly represent 4.5 percent of the overall population (Uganda Bureau of Statistics, 2018). Furthermore, in Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa and the seventh most populated globally, there are 10.9 million older individuals, based on data from 2020 (He et al., 2020). Egypt, Ethiopia, and South Africa each have elderly populations exceeding 5 million (Agyemang, 2025).

A report from the World Health Organisation in 2021 indicated that global populations are ageing at a more rapid pace than in previous years, and this demographic shift will influence nearly all facets of life. The report further revealed that the majority of the one billion individuals aged over 60 are located in low- and middle-income nations, predominantly in African countries. This situation poses significant threats to their quality of life and creates numerous obstacles that impede their full participation in society, as essential resources for a fulfilling life remain largely inaccessible to many in these regions (Longev, 2021).

In contemporary African societies, the traditional institution responsible for caregiving is undergoing dismantlement. This institution, namely the extended family, is experiencing disintegration (John 2011). As a result, the ageing population is now confronted with various issues. These issues have posed significant challenges for older individuals. In Nigeria, this class of individuals are facing a lot of challenges, which prompted the study to investigate the dilemma faced by the aged in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Nigeria, elderly individuals endure significant hardships in our modern society (Hamilton, 2006; Ajufo, 2019). They represent the most impoverished segment of the population, with clear evidence of destitution and begging among them (Ajufo, 2019). A brief examination of the Federal Government of Nigeria's implementation of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) shows that this vulnerable demographic has received little to no attention. This constitutes a substantial issue (Ajufo, 2019). Moreover, existing statistics indicate that developed countries have experienced the most pronounced ageing, while many developing nations are only just beginning to fully undergo the ageing transition (UNDESA, 2013; Goodrick & Pelsler, 2014; Ajufo, 2019).

Ageing is a gradual process, but its visible effects are difficult to predict. Furthermore, it is a relatively recent phenomenon in developing societies, with little historical precedent. Even in developed countries, which have implemented various policies and programmes, adjusting to the challenges posed by an ageing population has not been entirely smooth. Since significant changes in age structure are occurring over a relatively short period in developing nations, it suggests that these countries will have less time than their developed counterparts to address issues caused by demographic shifts (United Nations, 2001). Consequently, the rapid pace of population ageing has serious implications for government policies, including healthcare, social security, and economic growth (Ajufo, 2019).

With relatively low levels of social and economic development and limited access to adequate healthcare, a country like Nigeria will struggle to address the challenges posed by a large elderly population, especially as traditional family structures that support the elderly decline (Abanyam, 2013; Okoye, 2012). The position of the elderly in Nigeria is becoming increasingly unpredictable due to the declining support provided to them. On this backdrop, this research sought to examine the dilemma of the aged in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study was carried out under two specific objectives, which are:

To examine how the aged are marginalised in decision-making in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

To examine how the aged are marginalised in the distribution of relief palliatives within Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Ageing

Ageing is a universal experience shared by all humans. As noted by Edeh (2014), ageing refers to changes that significantly reduce the likelihood of survival, resulting from processes that are universal, inevitable, and irreversible within the individual. It encompasses a multidimensional process involving physical, psychological, and social changes that accumulate in a person over time. Ageing is characterised as the developmental and ongoing processes of transformation in an individual from conception until death (Atchley 1980). In simpler terms, it refers to the act or process of growing old. Ageing is frequently examined from three interconnected viewpoints – physical, psychological, and social. Ageing in humans

pertains to a multifaceted process involving physical, psychological, and social changes. Ageing represents the gradual progression towards the maximum lifespan of a human being (Taber's Encyclopedia Medical Dictionary, 2004). This process commences at conception and persists throughout an individual's life. The changes associated with ageing manifest at various chronological ages and advance at differing rates. Some changes are visibly apparent in physical appearance and abilities, while others are internal and not easily observable (Togonu-Bickersteth, 2014).

Ageing is an unavoidable process that leads to physical decline in all body parts. Conversely, population ageing refers to the phenomenon where older individuals constitute a larger proportion of the overall population. There is no widely recognized definition of older individuals. This is due to the absence of a universally accepted standard for classifying specific groups of people as elderly (Oluwabamide 2005). Consequently, the classification of individuals as old is rather subjective. In contemporary society, old age has a legal definition, as it pertains to the age at which the majority of individuals cease working, and where claims for certain types of welfare benefits, such as pensions, can be submitted (Gidens 1990).

Perception of the Aged in the Traditional Setting

In traditional Nigerian society, old age was greatly esteemed and celebrated as "the age of wisdom and teaching." Elderly individuals were held in high regard as the bearers of inherited wisdom and experience, and they were recognised as the primary decision-makers (Adeleke, 2014; Eboiyehi, 2015). Apt (2000) notes that in African traditional societies, old age was perceived as a blessing, with the aged being respected and honoured. They were also viewed as representatives of the ancestors and as custodians of cultural traditions (Sagner, 2001). However, this perspective has shifted in contemporary times. With modernisation, the younger generation tends to view old age as a challenging and "problematic" stage of life (Eboiyehi, 2015; Edeh, 2014). The elderly are often regarded as less useful to society. Furthermore, the wealth of knowledge possessed by the elderly is frequently seen as outdated and obsolete rather than a source of wisdom.

Additionally, in traditional Nigerian society, elderly individuals were typically well-connected and cared for by their families. The extended family system played a crucial role in providing care for the elderly, with support coming from family members such as wives, children, sons, and daughters-in-law (Edeh, 2014). However, modernisation has led to changes in family structures in Nigeria, disintegrating the extended family system (Abanyam, 2013). Consequently, the traditional role of the family in caring for and supporting elderly members is gradually diminishing (Aboderin, 2006).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Disengagement Theory

In order to comprehend the concept of ageing as examined in this paper, it may be essential to briefly address its theoretical foundation that pertains to this research.

The Disengagement Theory is a social psychological theory of ageing that was introduced by Elaine Cumming and William Henry in their 1961 publication, *Growing Old*. Their research involved 275 men and women aged between 50 and 90, and it was founded on the observation that ageing entails a gradual surrender of social roles and a reduction in social interactions.

Cumming and Henry contend that both individuals and society prepare for the eventual disengagement (death) through a gradual, mutually advantageous process in which both parties withdraw from each other. They state: "In our theory, ageing is an unavoidable mutual withdrawal or disengagement, leading to diminished interaction between the ageing individual and others within the social system to which he or she belongs. This process may be initiated by the individual or by others in the environment. The ageing person may withdraw more significantly from certain groups while remaining relatively close to others. This withdrawal may be accompanied from the outset by an increased focus on oneself; certain societal institutions may facilitate this withdrawal. Once the ageing process is complete, the balance that existed in middle age between the individual and society will transition to a new balance characterised by greater distance and a different type of relationship" (Abanyam, 2013).

In the study, older persons in traditional society were seen as custodians of norms and traditions that govern social morals and relationships. Their disengagement occurred through death and was regarded as a transition to ancestral roles, which kept the aged linked to their community even in death. In contemporary Ikot Ekpene society, however, the disengagement of the aged appears unruly, despite their ongoing functional roles in the area. This has led to certain challenges affecting the living conditions and well-being of the elderly in the study area.

The Activity Theory

The focus here is on the ongoing performance of roles. This stands in contrast to the disengagement theory, which highlights the withdrawal from roles. In relation to this activity theory, the primary concept is that when roles are lost, such as during retirement or widowhood, the individual is expected to seek substitutes. This theory explicitly states that: "The older individual who ages optimally is the one who remains active and manages to counteract the reduction of his social environment. He continues the activities of middle age for as long as possible and subsequently finds replacements for work when compelled to retire; replacements for friends and loved ones who are lost due to death" (Ajufo, 2019). This theory posits that society withdraws from the elderly individual, yet this occurs against the individual's will or desire. It further suggests that, to mitigate this withdrawal, the individual should strive to remain engaged, keep busy, and maintain a youthful spirit (Ajufo, 2019).

The situation of the aged, as described by activity theory, involves the traditional roles that elders play within the community. Most elders, after retirement, find it necessary to dedicate their time to community affairs. In accordance with activity theory, the elders in Ikot Ekpene regard their age cohort as the suitable time to participate in community administration, which tradition attributes to elders due to their experience and maturity, along with their capacity to take on responsibilities. However, there has been a shift, and the elders' role now appears to be under threat in contemporary times.

Methodology

Survey research design was engaged by the researcher for the study. The study was conducted in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Ikot Ekpene, also known as The Raffia City, is a historic town in the south-southern state of Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. It is the political and cultural capital of the Annang ethnic group in Nigeria (Nair, 1972). The town is located on the A342 highway that parallels the coast, between Calabar to

the southeast and Aba to the west, with the state capital, Uyo, on this road just to the east. Umuahia is the next major town to the north. The population of the Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area was estimated to be 180,500 in 2022. Ikot Ekpene is known as a regional centre of commerce, with notable exports of palm products, especially palm oil, kernels, raffia products, including raffia fibres and its wine, and ground crops of yams, cassava, taro, and corn. The population is made up primarily of the Annang people with a small number of Igbo traders and Hausa Suya vendors. Significant exports also include basket weaving, sculpture, and, most notably, raffia cane furniture (hence the colloquial name of the town) (Ette, 2020).

Ikot Ekpene is also known for its technological innovations due to the emergence of Future Laboratories, an innovation hub dedicated to training young technical talents and helping entrepreneurs build tech start-ups in Ikot Ekpene in partnership with organisations like NITDA and JICA. The Raffia City Entrepreneurs Scheme committee was inaugurated by Hon. John Cleton Etim. Ikot Ekpene is also the headquarters of some notable seminaries and the Catholic Diocese in the south-south region of Nigeria. The Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, and Ritman University is located in the city. The city houses the notable mini stadium at GRA road, Nteps Super Markets, Four Point by Sheraton Hotels, etc (Ette, 2020)

The population for the study was considered to be 673,475, which is a projected population at 2025 from population stats.com (2025). Being a qualitative research, the sample size of the study was determined through the Fetterman's big-net approach to be study participants who took part in the study. Study participants were randomly selected by the researchers from the streets, roads, shops, and market places in Utu Ikpe, Mbiaso, and Ifuho communities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Fatterman's big-net approach was adopted for sampling technique and the determination of sample size. According to Fatterman (2010), the researchers embarked on the fieldwork with a fishermen's ideology of interviewing participants who are ready to take part in the study who later form the sample size of the study, after deciding on the age cohorts for the study participants. Data were collected through the use of an interview guide unto the point of saturation.

Data were collected through the in-depth interview, key informant interview and researchers observations. Collected data were analysed thematically with key variables from the objectives of the study becoming the key themes for the analysis of the data. Findings were analysed thematically.

Findings

Marginalisation of the Aged

The majority of the study participants thought that the wave of political activities have after the value for the aged in the present Ikot Ekpene society. This they opined was because of the high level of participation of the young adults who see politics as their main source of income and livelihood in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. Due to the reckless participation of the young people in politics and the fact that political affairs have come to direct other community affairs, in that, politicians influence what goes on and who is who at the community level. This scenario has brought about a degree of violation of moral respects and values for the elders on the ground that they are not really active or relevant in the field of politics. According to one of the study participants, he narrated that;

You know we are in the era of politics and politics decide everything now a days. What I mean is that politicians decide everything now in our communities. I mean in our villages. I mean that even our village heads are controlled by the politicians. So, since the youths are the ones they use for politics, these youths now feel that they are more powerful in the communities than the elders. They feel that the value of the elders is no more or less as in compare to them. So, we now have a society whereby the youths do not consider the elders relevant beings in the plan of affairs but only those who they give remnants of what they eat. The elders who were once treated with respects are facing a generation without value for the elderly (Male, 57 years, artist, interviewed at Mbiaso on 17th July 2025).

Another study participant has this to say;

The elders are not regarded as before in this village. Before, the elders were respected and held in high regard because they were respected by the government and politicians of those days. In fact, the politicians used to go and consult the elders before they meet with the people of the village. But it has change now. Politic is have cause a lot of changes. Now, the people may go and do their things without consulting the elders. So, the elders are benefitting much as before from the blessing of governance which was not so in the past. Now, it is the young people who even do the sharing and then decide what to give to the elders. There is no more respects for the elders as before. This has caused them to keep the elders aside from much of the things they do (Female, 49 years, trader, interviewed at Utu Ikpe on 13th July 2025)

Data gathered interviews revealed that the marginalisation of the elderly among the people of Ikot Ekpene is influenced by circular politics of the government of the day. The high level of participation of the youths forced the young people to neglect the custodians of their traditional, norms, morals and the sacred life of their society by ways of upholding, preserving and transferring the society norms from one generation to another.

The recent economic crises have forced the government at all levels to provide relief materials at one point or the other especially during the COVID-199 and post COVIC-19 period. Most of the relief materials have been targeting at the aged in most communities as welfare relief responsibilities by the government. Gathered data revealed that the aged have been neglected in the distribution of these relief materials by the young people and few persons who are in charge of this programme especially at the community or the grassroots level. Study participants reported that most of the palliatives that were meant for the aged were diverted thereby leading to the neglect of the elderly in most communities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. One of the study participants reported that;

It is true that the elders have been neglected. The truth is that the elders have lost their influence because the youths these days are constantly threatening with crises if they don't have their ways at events. So, for peace, the elders will always give them their ways and at the end, they will go away with supposed to be given to the elders with their own. Like a time the government sent palliatives for the old people, the young people who were sent by the government did not do what they were sent to do. They diverted those items and a lot of the older people did not have access to those items. It is very bad what they have been doing and the government will think that they are helping the old people in the villages but that is not true because the young people responsible for distributing these items to the old people do not do it accordingly (Female, 42 years, civil servant, interviewed at Ifuho village on 15th July 2025)

Another study participant reported that;

You have to understand that we do not have anything from this people because they do not have respect for their elders any more. It is a generation problem. These days, children do not have respect for their parents anymore. So what do you expect? They now treat us as if it is a crime for one to get old. I used to tell my children that they should know that every day they see, they are growing to old age. These children do not care much anymore. If they are given something to give us, they do not have the consciousness of morality, to give it to us. They feel there is nothing wrong in them taking what belong to us. Like the time the governor as giving food items through food relief programme. My brother, those young people played trick with network and went away with the items till today (Male, retiree, 71 years, interviewed at Mbiaso village on 17th July 2025).

Gathered data have revealed that most of the elderly persons in Ikot Ekpene are neglected in terms of distribution of palliatives despite their roles as custodians of traditions, norms, morals, and rites of passage among the people. The majority of the study participants were of the verdict that the young people who are always in charge of palliatives do used the opportunity to deny the aged their privileges by not giving to them what were meant for them.

Discussion of Findings

Marginalisation of the aged was a key theme in the data gathered from the field through interviews, discussion and observations. Emergence from gathered data revealed that the influence of politics over the Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area have brought about marginalisation of the aged due to the believe that the aged do not fit into their political activities and patterns of winning elections. Findings revealed that the young people through political activities have disengaged the elders from most of the activities of governance. This by implications, based of findings of the study unveiled that the aged are marginalised in decision making through which findings unveiled that decision are taken at political level without the consultations of the elders in most cases. This finding give credence to Ajufo (2019) who posit that in Nigeria, elderly individuals endure significant hardships in our modern society.

Emergence from gathered data through interviews and discussions revealed that the majority of the aged in Ikot Ekpene Local Government of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria have been neglected in various relief programmes of the federal, state, local government and non-governmental organisations. Findings revealed that the young people who are always responsible to distributions of these relief materials and items, do divert lots of the relief materials and life sustainable items which were meant for the aged for their selfish interests. This act has positioned the aged in the state of neglect and disengaged in the distributions of relief materials. These findings agreed with Abanyam (2013); Okoye (2012) who posit that with a relatively low levels of social and economic development and limited access to adequate healthcare, a country like Nigeria will struggle to address the challenges posed by a large elderly population, especially as traditional family structures that support the elderly decline.

Conclusion

This study examined the dilemma of the aged as marginalised citizens in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The elderly persons have suffered

marginalisation in decision making among the people due to the influence of politics which is the main governing force of the society through the state and local governments. This have empowered the youths to take most of the decisions without consulting the aged thereby reducing the value and respect of the elders in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. The dilemma of the aged here also involve neglect in the distributions of relief items or palliatives in the relief and life support programmes of the federal and state government. The aged are neglected as the family support system is failing due to recent attitude of the young people in this contemporary society.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made;

The government should establish a dedicated ministry, such as “Ministry of the Aged Affairs,” to enhance the social well-being of the elderly which will checkmate marginalisation of the aged in the local government area.

Relief items and palliatives should be distributed by the elderly to the members of their age cohorts.

Government should propagate political relevance for the elders in the state and Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area specifically.

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